

ECONOMY

ECONOMETRIC MODEL OF THE CYCLICAL FUNCTIONING OF THE NATIONAL ECONOMY IN THE LONG-TERM PERSPEKTIVE (ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE NATIONAL ECONOMY OF AZERBAIJAN)

Ayyubov M.

*Leading research fellow, Institute of Economics
Ministry of Science and Education of the Republic of Azerbaijan
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2255-1706>*

Abstract

The article discusses the methodological foundations for the development of a “conjunctural-structural” macro-econometric model of the cyclical functioning of the country’s national economy. It argued that, along with various processes that are cyclical in the country’s economy, the country’s economy as a whole at the macro level operates in a cyclical mode. One cycle of functioning consists of the stages of development and decline in the rate of development, crisis, decline and stabilization. At the stage of development of the country’s economy, an intra-system economic threat to the state structure does not arise. Intra-system economic threats to the state structure manifest themselves at the stages of declining growth rates of economic development and crisis. Therefore, it is necessary to have tools with the help of which one could determine the time of formation of stages of declining growth rates and the manifestation of crisis situation in the country’s economy. We believe that by developing a “conjunctural-structural” macro-econometric model of the cyclical functioning of the country’s national economy, it is possible to determine the possible time of onset of economic threats to the state structure and prepare a program for eliminating threats beforehand.

Keywords: cyclical economic process; econometric model; cyclical functioning of the country's national economy; “conjunctural-structural” macro econometric model; economic threats to the state structure.

Methodology. The research methodology is a systems approach, the basic principles of the general theory of dynamic systems. To compile a “conjunctural-structural” equation for a macro-econometric model of the cyclical functioning of the country’s national economy, the author of the article has developed a methodology based on statistical-economic, calculation-constructive, econometric methods of cognition.

Based on the research methodology developed by the author of the article, an algorithm for performing calculations to compile a “conjunctural-structural” equation of a macro-econometric model of the cyclical functioning of the country’s national economy constructed.

Introduction. Since the mid-19th century, many scientific works published explaining the essence and content of cyclical processes of various durations in the country's economy. The American economist, representative of the neoclassical economic school E.H. Hansen in the 30s of the last century systematized ideas about the economic cycles occurring in the national economy of the country [1]. In modern macroeconomic theory, related to investments directed into the national economy of the country, the following cycles are distinguished:

1. The role of growth and decline in investment volume.
2. Analysis of the dynamics of factors determining the volume of investment: graph of the limits of investment efficiency suitable for interest rates.
3. Dynamics of technical, natural resource, territorial factors, as well as population growth factors that determine the volume of investments and their impact on the cyclical nature of the functioning of the country’s economy.

4. Chain characteristics of investments related to the development of innovations, scientific, and technological progress (Schumpeter);

5. Long-term production of elements of fixed assets, the impact of the durability of fixed capital on economic systems.

6. Initial impulses that create economic processes caused by economic growth, which have an oscillatory, cyclical nature.

Also, in economic theory, there are several types of macroeconomic cycles, differing in the duration of the periods. Modern concepts of macroeconomic cycles of various durations can be grouped as follows.

1. Short-term cycles with a period of 3-5 years. 3-5-year short-term cycles include: the life cycle of manufactured products (service life of product types) Schumpeter, associated with innovation; K. Kitchen’s cycles associated with world gold reserves and vital material reserves; cycles of K. Marx and E. Hansen of uneven reproduction of working capital in the country’s economy.

2. Medium-term 8-12 year cycles associated with fixed production assets. These types of cycles include the cycles of K. Marx on the massive renewal of fixed assets of production, as well as the cycles of K. Juglar on the influence of monetary factors associated with the activities of banks on the period of change in fixed capital.

3. Long-term 15-25-year cycles of the American economist, Nobel Prize winner S. Kuznets, related to the demographic situation in the country, migration, construction, including the renewal of infrastructure facilities.

4. Long-term (more than 40 years) oscillatory cycles of N. Kondratiev, associated with the economic situation, that is, with the situation and with the state of social reproduction. N. Kondratiev, based on statistical data from European countries (period 1800-1920), having studied the functioning of national economies, concluded that national economies in the long term (40-60 years), depending on the situation, have an oscillatory nature.

Discussion. Conjuncture factors include factors that influence the elements of the reproduction process, consisting of the stages of production, exchange, income distribution and consumption.

According to N. Kondratiev and followers of Kondratiev's theory, due to the fact that the functioning of national economies, as well as large regional economic systems over a long period (40-60 years) is of an oscillatory nature. These vibrations have a "long-wave" characteristic [203]. However, neither Kondratiev nor

his followers proposed an econometric model assessing the "long-wave" oscillatory activity of the national economy.

In studies of the functioning of the national economy of different countries, the American economist R.G. Hawtry [400] concluded that macroeconomic fluctuations in the functioning of the national economy do not depend on technological progress, capital accumulation or population growth. Macroeconomic fluctuations are a secondary indicator of development, and they are just fluctuations. In reality, the country's economy has the character of development, and indicators characterizing fluctuations are secondary indicators and are not important.

We believe that, along with cycles of economic processes of different nature and duration, in the longer term (more than 30 years) the country's national economy operates in a cyclical mode.

Diagram 1: schematic model of the functioning of the country's national economy in the long-term (more than 30 years) period.

In the mid-20th century, US economists A. Burns and W. K. Mitchell [398] proposed a concept that explains the essence of the cyclical functioning of the country's economy over 25-30 years.

According to the authors, business activity in the national economy of the country, that is, the production of material products and the provision of services, flows along a straight line, characterized by long-term development along the Y curve, which rises and falls around the trend $\tilde{Y}$ (diagram). However, the authors believed that in the long term, the development of the country's economy has a direct trend of constant growth $\tilde{Y}$, and the factors shaping the production of material products and the provision of services Y have virtually no effect on the direct trend $\tilde{Y}$.

In our opinion, the American economists A. Burns and W. K. Mitchell, in their studies of the cyclical nature of the functioning of the country's economy in the long term, came to the wrong conclusion.

So firstly, in classical and neoclassical economic theories it believed to be that the functioning of national economic systems has a cyclical nature, consisting of

stages: development $\rightarrow$ slowdown development $\rightarrow$ crisis $\rightarrow$ decline $\rightarrow$ stabilization (Diagram.1).

Secondly, the indicator of production and provision of services Y, expressing the result of the functioning of the national economy, depends on changes in fixed capital, working capital, labor, money supply, as well as from the multiplier effect of investments and the effect of acceleration of production volumes, provision of services.

Thirdly, in the long term, the dependence of the trend parameter of the country's economic development $\tilde{y}$ on the actual parameter of production of goods and provision of services y, is measured by a linear function

$$\tilde{y} = a_0 + a_1 \cdot y$$

As can be seen from the function, provided that parameters a_0 and a_1 remain constant, large values of the parameter y correspond to large values of the parameter $\tilde{y}$, and small values of the parameter y correspond to small values of the parameter $\tilde{y}$.

Conclusions. We believe that, along with cyclical economic processes that differ in essence and duration, in the longer term (more than 30 years) the country's national economy operates in a cyclical mode. (Diagram 1).

In contrast to the opinion of the American economist R.G. Hawtry, we believe that the country's economy has the character of development at a certain stage. The indicators characterizing fluctuations are the primary indicators that form the growth rate of development.

In addition, in contrast to the opinion of American economists A. Burns and W. K. Mitchell, we believe that in the long term, the development of the country's economy has a direct trend of constant growth $\tilde{Y}$, and the factors that shape the production of products and the provision of services Y shape the development trend.

$$f(x) = a_0/2 + \sum_{k=1}^m (a_k \cdot \cos kt + b_k \cdot \sin kt), \quad k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, m, \quad (2)$$

That is:

$$\tilde{y}^S = \tilde{y} + f(x) = (c_0 + c_1 \cdot t) + f(t), \quad (3)$$

Or,

$$\tilde{y}^S = (c_0 + a/2 + c_1 \cdot t) + \sum_{k=1}^m (a_k \cdot \cos kt + b_k \cdot \sin kt), \quad k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, m, \quad (4)$$

In this case, the parameters $\tilde{y}^S$ of the cyclic process are expressed by the trigonometric Fourier function with a period of 2π . Dividing the parameter of an empirical series of a cyclic process into trigonometric Fourier series is considered a Problem of harmonic analysis [264, pp. 165-169; 129, pp. 418-419; 344, p. 427-463].

We believe that the function expressing the dynamics of the indicator of total output $\tilde{y}^S$ for the period T

$$\tilde{y}^S = (c_0 + a/2 + c_1 \cdot t) + \sum_{k=1}^m (a_k \cdot \cos kt + b_k \cdot \sin kt), \quad k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, m, \quad (4)$$

is a "conjunctural-structural" function, expressing a change in the structure of gross output, depending on the conjuncture of the functioning of the national economy in the long term.

According to the method we proposed, when expressing the parameters of the $\tilde{y}^S$ of a periodic process using the trigonometric Fourier function, harmonic series are calculated that approximate a given empirical series, and a function with a correlation coefficient of the highest harmonic order is selected.

When expressing the parameters of a periodic series using the trigonometric Fourier function, the parameters of the Fourier series are determined using the following system of equations:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} a_0 &= 2 \cdot \Sigma(y - \tilde{y}) / n \\ a_k &= 2 \cdot [\Sigma(y - \tilde{y}) \cdot \cos kt] / n \\ b_k &= 2 \cdot [\Sigma(y - \tilde{y}) \cdot \sin kt] / n \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (5)$$

In the system of equations (5): y is an indicator of the dynamics of the empirical series, $\tilde{y}$ is an indicator of the dynamics of the aligned empirical series; n is the number of years of the empirical series; t – expression of time sequence (T) in radians:

We believe that in the long term, the development of the country's economy has a constantly increasing $\tilde{Y}$ -direct trend. However, the factors that shape the Y row have a direct impact on the trend line $\tilde{Y}$ (diagram 1).

Methodology for developing an econometric model of the cyclical functioning of the national economy in the long-term (more than 30 years) period.

The parameter $\tilde{y}^S$, characterizing the periodic process, can be expressed as the algebraic sum of the reduced parameter $\tilde{y}$ of the empirical series y for time t :

$$\tilde{y} = (c_0 + c_1 \cdot t), \quad (1)$$

And the parameter of the empirical series y , expanded into a trigonometric Fourier series $f(x)$:

$t = (0.2\pi/n, 2 \cdot 2\pi/n, 3 \cdot 2\pi/n, \dots, (n-1) \cdot 2\pi/n, 2\pi)$;
 k - the number of harmonics that bring the Fourier series closer to the empirical series.

Algorithm for compiling a macroeconomic model of the cyclical functioning of the country's national economy

We believe that the macroeconomic model of the cyclical functioning of the national economy in the long-term (more than 30 years) period must be compiled according to the equations we proposed (1), (2), (3), (4), (5).

The macroeconomic "conjunctural-structural" model of the cyclical functioning of the national economy in the long term (more than 30 years) is compiled in the following sequence.

1. At the first stage, the dynamics of the empirical indicator of total output over the past (more than 30 years) period in the country's national economy is examined. If the graph of the dynamics of the empirical indicator of total output y for the period under study shows signs of cyclicity, begin the study.

2. Dynamics of the aggregate output volume parameter y levels off in a straight line

$$\tilde{Y} = (c_0 + c_1 \cdot T), \quad (1)$$

3. The indicator $\sum u$ is calculated as the sum of the differences between the empirical series of total production output y and the calculated indicator $\tilde{y}$:

$$\sum u = \sum (y - \tilde{y}), \quad (5)$$

4. The expression of moments of the time period T , in t radians, for the purpose of decomposing the empirical series of the total volume of output of goods and services Y into the trigonometric Fourier series is calculated by the formula

$$t = 2\pi \cdot T/n, \quad (6)$$

In formula (6): n is an indicator of the number of moments in the time period T , measured in years. In calculations when expressing the time period T in terms of t radians, the initial year of the time period T is assumed to be zero. For example, if the time period T covers 30 years, then the expression for n moments of period T in t radians is calculated as:

$$t = (0; 1 \cdot 2\pi/30; 2 \cdot 2\pi/30; 3 \cdot 2\pi/30; \dots; 29 \cdot 2\pi/30), \quad (7)$$

5. The harmony of the first row $\tilde{Y}^S I$ at values $k = 1$ is calculated in the following sequence.

5.1. The trigonometric functions $\cos t$ and $\sin t$ are calculated in radians;

5.2. Parameters $\sum(u \cdot \cos t)$ and $\sum(u \cdot \sin t)$ are calculated;

$$k = 2, \cos 2t \text{ и } \sin 2t, \sum(u \cdot \cos 2t) \text{ и } \sum(u \cdot \sin 2t), a_2 = (2/n) \cdot \sum(u \cdot \cos 2t); b_2 = (2/n) \cdot \sum(u \cdot \sin 2t), \quad (11)$$

$$\tilde{Y}^S_{II} = (c_0 + a_0/2) + c_1 \cdot T + a_1 \cdot \cos t + b_1 \cdot \sin t + a_2 \cdot \cos 2t + b_2 \cdot \sin 2t, \quad (12)$$

2) Third harmony $\tilde{Y}^S_{III}$, with values:

$$k = 3, \cos 3t \text{ и } \sin 3t, \sum(u \cdot \cos 3t) \text{ и } \sum(u \cdot \sin 3t), a_3 = (2/n) \cdot \sum(u \cdot \cos 3t); b_3 = (2/n) \cdot \sum(u \cdot \sin 3t), \quad (13)$$

$$\tilde{Y}^S_{III} = (c_0 + a_0/2) + c_1 \cdot T + a_1 \cdot \cos t + b_1 \cdot \sin t + a_2 \cdot \cos 2t + b_2 \cdot \sin 2t + a_3 \cdot \cos 3t + b_3 \cdot \sin 3t \quad (12)$$

And so on.

Calculations continue until the maximum value r_{MAX} obtained.

Thus, we believe that, based on the methodology we propose, it is possible to form a “conjunctural-structural” econometric model of the cyclical functioning of the country’s national economy in the distant future. By calculating the normative forecasts for the indicator of total output in the national economy, as well as socio-economic indicators arising from the indicator of total output, it is possible to assess the possible state of the country’s national economy in the distant future.

Compilation of an econometric model of the cyclical functioning of the national economy of Azerbaijan in 1965-2000.

The national economy of the Republic of Azerbaijan until 1992 of the 20th century functioned as part of the national economic system of the USSR. As result of the collapse of the national economic system of the USSR state, in the 90s of the last century, the national economy of the Republic of Azerbaijan transformed from a structure based on a social formation into a new structure of a market economy.

During the study, we believed that the essence of the theoretical provisions of the mechanism of production and provision of services in the period 1965-1992 and in the period 1992-2000 in the national economy of Azerbaijan has not changed.

5.3. The parameters a_0, a_1, b_1 of the trigonometric Fourier series are calculated using the formulas:

$$a_0 = (2/n) \cdot \sum u; a_1 = (2/n) \cdot \sum(u \cdot \cos t); b_1 = (2/n) \cdot \sum(u \cdot \sin t), \quad (8)$$

5.4. Based on the calculated parameters a_0, a_1, b_1 , the Fourier trigonometric series $f(x)$ is calculated:

$$f(t)_I = a_0/2 + a_1 \cdot \cos t + b_1 \cdot \sin t, \quad (9)$$

Thus, with the cyclical functioning of the national economy of the country, the calculation equation of the “conjuncture-structural” model - the dynamics of gross output in the long term in the first harmony is expressed by the function:

$$\tilde{Y}^S_I = (c_0 + a_0/2) + c_1 \cdot T + a_1 \cdot \cos t + b_1 \cdot \sin t, \quad (10)$$

The correlation coefficient calculated between the empirical series of gross output Y and the series of dynamics of gross output $\tilde{Y}^S_I$ in the first harmony.

If the calculated value of the correlation coefficient RI is between the values of $0.950 \leq r \leq 1.000$, then it considered there is a high relationship between the calculated first harmonic series $\tilde{Y}^S I$ and the empirical series of total output Y the relationship is high.

5.5. The equation of the “conjunctural-structural” model is calculated:

1) Second harmony $\tilde{Y}^S_{II}$, with values:

Based on information from the State Committee for Statistics of Azerbaijan, we have compiled statistical data on the indicator of the total output of products and services in Azerbaijan for the period 1965-2020.

Research has shown that the period of one full cycle of functioning of the national economy of Azerbaijan is 35-36 years. It was determined that the national economy of Azerbaijan: in the period 1965-1984 functioned at the stage of development; in the period 1984-1990 at the stage slowdown and crisis; in the period 1990-1995 during the recession; and in the period 1995-2000 at the stage of stabilization.

The compilation of the “conjunctural-structural” econometric model was carried out in the following sequence.

1. Dynamics of Y volumes of gross output of the national economy of Azerbaijan during the study period 1965-2000, in 2000 prices, aligned by linear function

$$\tilde{Y} = 0,0036 \cdot T + 0,5048.$$

In the resulting linear function: T – time points for 1965-2000; 0.0036 – average annual increase in the dynamics of total output of products and services in 2000 prices; the value 0.5048 represents the initial value of the aligned time series of total output at 2000 prices.

2. The indicator ($\sum u$) calculated.

3. Moments of the time period T are expressed in t radians:

$$t = (0; 1 \ 2\pi/30; 2 \ 2\pi/30; 3 \ 2\pi/30...; 35 \ 2\pi/36).$$

4. Calculated by:

$$\cos t, \cos 2t, \cos 3t \vee \sin t, \sin 2t, \sin 3t$$

5. Calculated by:

$$\sum(u \cdot \cos t), \sum(u \cdot \cos 2t), \sum(u \cdot \cos 3t), \sum(u \cdot \sin t), \sum(u \cdot \sin 2t), \sum(u \cdot \sin 3t).$$

6. The functions $\tilde{Y}^S_I, \tilde{Y}^S_{II}, \tilde{Y}^S_{III}$ of the harmonic series $k = (1,2,3)$ of gross output are compiled.

Calculations showed that in the period 1965-2000 the “conjunctural-structural” equation of the full cycle functioning of the national economy of Azerbaijan in third harmony ($k=3$), at $r = 0.977$ is expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{Y}^S_{III} = & 0,5041 + 0,0036 \cdot T - 0,318 \cdot \cos t - 0,016 \cdot \sin t + 0,052 \cdot \cos 2t + 0,095 \cdot \sin 2t + \\ & + 0,036 \cdot \cos 3t - 0,021 \cdot \sin 3t. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, based on our research, we came to the conclusion that:

- 1) the national economy of Azerbaijan operates in a cyclical mode in the long-term period;
- 2) the period of one complete cycle is 35-36 years.
- 3) it was determined that in the twentieth century, in the period 1894-2000, the national economy of Azerbaijan functioned in three complete cycles;
- 4) from the beginning of the new 21st century, from 2001, the national economy of Azerbaijan began to function in a new 35-36 flight cycle;

Based on statistical data from the State Statistics Committee of the Republic, it was established that the economy of Azerbaijan from 2001 to 2014 functioned at the stage of development. And starting from 2015, the pace of economic development began to decline. So, it was established that, if the average annual rate of total output of products and provision of services at the development stage was 20.5%, after 2014, the average annual growth rate of total output of products and provision of services tended to decrease and amounted to (-0.1)%.

We believe that using our proposed methodology for compiling a “conjunctural-structural” macro-econometric model of the cyclical functioning of the country’s national economy, it is possible to draw conclusions about the history of the functioning of the country’s economy in the distant past, and based on the forecasts compiled, conclusions can be drawn about the state of the country’s national economy in the long-term future period.

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